

New information about the distribution of the western conifer seed bug *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Syria

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ABSTRACT: New records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Syria are reported. *L. occidentalis* has been observed in Duraykish, Coastal area; Mazraat Deir Al-Ashayer, west of Damascus and Urman, As-Sweida, southern Syria. Information on the distribution of this invasive species in the neighboring areas has been documented, too.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera; Coreidae; *Leptoglossus occidentalis*; new records; Syria; East Mediterranean Region.

To cite this article: Almatni, W. S., 2024, New information about the distribution of the Western conifer seed bug *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Syria, *J.Het.Turk.*, 6(1):9-13

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11350169

To link to this article: <https://www.j-ht.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/V61-A3.pdf>

Received: Mar 3, 2024; **Revised:** Apr 16,2024; **Accepted:** Apr 18, 2024; **Published online:** May 31, 2024

INTRODUCTION

The Western conifer seed bug *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Heteroptera: Coreidae) is a highly dispersible Nearctic coreid native to western North America. It invaded the old world and colonized the major part of Europe since its first appearance in Italy, near Vicenza (Veneto region) in 1999 (Tescari, 2001) (see EPPO

RS 2006/160). This species has been reported from several European countries, especially in the Mediterranean Region (van der Heyden, 2019; van der Heyden & Zettel, 2019). *Leptoglossus occidentalis* is considered an invasive alien species spreading in Europe (EPPO Reporting Service no. 01 – 2010, Num. article:2010/009).

The first observation in Türkiye was in

Sariyer-Istanbul in 2009 (Arslangündođdu & Hizal, 2010), and the insect later spread to various cities of Türkiye (Fent & Kment, 2011; Hizal & Inan, 2012; Öttemiz & Dođanlar, 2015; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016; Özgen et al., 2017; Parlak, 2017; Yücel & Kivan, 2018; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Ođuzođlu & Avcı, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021) and reached Antalya in 2014. In south east Türkiye, near the Syrian border, Cihan Arıkan observed *L. occidentalis* in 01-11-2020 in Cumhuriyet, 80440 Osmaniye Merkez/Osmaniye, North Hatay, Türkiye (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/63945005>). Wantedhg observed *L. occidentalis* in 02-11-2023 in İskenderun Arsuz Yolu, Arsuz, Hatay, Türkiye (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/189747941>).

Recently, this insect has been recorded in the East Mediterranean: from Lebanon (Nemer, 2015; Nemer et al., 2019), the Golan Heights (van der Heyden, 2018), Israel (van der Heyden, 2019), and Palestine (Handal & Qumsiyeh, 2019). Jordan didn't report this invasive species yet.

Leptoglossus occidentalis made severe damage on pine cones in pine forests in Lebanon, and the government controlled it by chemical insecticides in 2015 and later (www.elnashra.com/news/2015).

The first observation in Syria was done by Re'ut Ben Elissar on 12-11-2016 in Odem (an Israeli settlement), near Baq'atha, Northern part of the Golan Heights (van der Heyden, 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Field check of the presence of *L. occidentalis* was done between September and November 2023

on several pine locations in Syria. Also, data survey and review in scientific sites, like the "Syrian Wildlife Hobbyists" on Facebook, and www.iNaturalist.org has been done.

RESULTS

Leptoglossus occidentalis Heidemann, 1910 has been mentioned in this study survey in three regions of Syria (Figs.1-3)

Figure 1. Nymphs, Coastal area: Soliman Hassan, 20-06-2021, 34.901, 36.147, Duraykish (Draykish), Tartous, Syria. Near a Pine forest.

Figure 2. Adults, Anti-Lebanon mountains Raef Hakim, 10-10-2021, 33.591, 36.047, Mazraat Deir Al-Ashayer, Anti-Lebanon Mountains, western Reef Damascus. In a Pine forest.

Figure 3. Adults, Alarab mountain (southern area): Wa'el Almatni, 29-09-2023 32.513533, 36.764582, Urman, Sweida, Syria. In a house near pine trees in the village.

These three observations represent three geographic regions in Syria: coastal mountains in the west, anti-Lebanon mountains in the middle western Syria, and As-Sweida mountains in the south (Fig. 4). Pine trees and forests are distributed in that areas.

DISCUSSION

The economic impact of this invasive insect is still not clear in East Mediterranean countries. Lebanon confirmed its economic damage of conifer forests. For example, at the beginning of the presence of this insect in Lebanon, Air Force helicopters sprayed insecticides to control the species over the fruitful pine forests in Mount Lebanon (Almatn). The mission included the areas of: Qarnayel, Salima, Al-Arbaniyah, Arsoun, Jourat Arsoun, Al-Qasiba, Zandouqa, Qartadah, Ras Al-Matn, Deir Al-Harf, Btakhnia, and Al-Kina. (Alnashra news, 2015). In Syria, although it has been mentioned a few

years ago, as this study explains, there is no economic damage recorded or observed.

Since *L. occidentalis* has become present in Syria, its spread in forests and gardens must be carefully investigated, and its potential damage should be studied, especially on stone pine *Pinus pinea*. This insect is also possible to be present in Jordan, since this research recorded it in an area about 30 km from the Jordanian border.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to present my thanks to Torsten van der Heyden (Hamburg, GERMANY) for his cooperation in identification of the insect sample and reviewing the manuscript of this article, and to the "Syrian Wildlife Hobbyists" on Facebook, for the discoveries and scientific information that they present while identifying organisms in the Syrian wildlife.

Figure 4. Distribution map of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* in Syria and neighboring areas (Red dots). Numbers besides the dots refer to the registration date sequence.

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